

ABOUT THE LIFE, WORK AND MOST TRANSLATED WORK OF THOMAS MORE

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Annotation: Thomas More is an English thinker, writer, humanist, canonized saint of the Catholic Church. Thomas More was the author of 280 Latin epigrams, translations and short poems. Thomas More was active in translations from ancient Greek, which in his day was much less popular than Latin.

Keywords: Thomas, Catholic, Protestant, Utopia, Church, Joke, Invocation of Spirits, Latin poems.

Thomas More was born on February 7, 1478 in London in the family of a judge. He was the second of six children. More attended St. Anthony's School, considered one of the best schools in London. Later, from 1490 to 1492, he served as a house page to John Morton, Archbishop of Canterbury and Lord Chancellor of England. Broad-minded and resourceful, More entered Oxford in 1492 and received a classical education. Studying under Thomas Linacre and William Grocyn, he became fluent in Latin and Greek. At his father's insistence, More left Oxford after only two years to study law at the New Inn, a hotel in London. Thomas More was interested in religion from his youth.

In 1503-1504, More lived near the Carthusian monastery outside the walls of London and participated in the religious activities of the monks. Although he admired their piety, More eventually decided to return to his former position and was elected to Parliament in 1504 and started a family the following year. Did not Therefore, he decided to withdraw from public life until the death of this sovereign and the coronation of his young son. From 1510, Thomas More served as sub-prefect of London. Seven years later, he entered the service of Henry Tudor, the eighth of his name, to rule England. In this administration, Moreau served as the monarch's right-hand man, first as a diplomat and then as his secretary. He was knighted in 1521 and later served as Chancellor of Lancaster. In 1529, Moreau was finally granted the position of Lord Chancellor by the grace of King Henry VIII.

Thomas More, revered in the Catholic Church as Saint Thomas More, was an English jurist, judge, social philosopher, writer, statesman, and prominent humanist of the Renaissance. Thomas More wrote fiction and satire. He wrote in English, Latin, Ancient Greek and Italian. Thomas More's History of King Richard III (c. 1513-1518)

The Four Last Things (c. 1522)

A Consoling Conversation Against Adversity (1534) A Joke (c. 1516)

Utopia (1516)

Latin Poems (1518, 1520)

Letter to Brixius (1520)

Responsio ad Lutherum (Response to Luther, 1523)

Dialogue on Heresies (1529, 1530)

Supplication of the Souls (1529)

Letter Against Frith (1532)

Utopia. More's most famous and controversial work, *Utopia*, is a science fiction work written in Latin. More completed the book, and the theologian Erasmus published it at Leuven in 1516, but it was only translated into English and published in his homeland in 1551 (16 years after his execution), and the 1684 translation is the most widely cited. More and narrator/traveler Raphael Hythlodæus discuss contemporary ills in Antwerp and describe the political arrangements of the fictional island nation of Utopia (from the Greek words "ou-topos" [no place] and "eu-topos" [good place]). In *Utopia*, the conflicting social life of European countries is contrasted with the idea of a perfectly ordered, rational social order in Utopia and its surroundings (Tallstoria, Nolandia, and Aircastle). In Utopia, due to the simplicity of the laws and the fact that social gatherings are open to the public (encouraging participants to behave well), there are no lawyers, communal property supplants private property, equal rights for men and women, and almost complete religious tolerance (except for atheists who are allowed but hated). Some consider the main message of the novel to be the social need for order and discipline rather than freedom. Paradoxically, Hythlodæus, who believes that philosophers should stay out of politics, addresses More's ultimate conflict between his humanitarian beliefs and his courtly duties as servants of the king, suggesting that these ethics will one day conflict with political reality.

In 1532, More resigned as Lord Chancellor due to ill health. The real reason for his departure was Henry VIII's break with Rome and the creation of the Anglican Church; Mor was against it. In addition, Thomas More was very angry that England had left the "true faith" and did not come to the crown of the king's new wife, Anne Boleyn. Naturally, Henry VIII noticed this. On April 17, 1535, he was imprisoned in the Tower, found guilty of treason and beheaded on July 6, 1535. For his devotion to Catholicism, Mor was canonized by the Roman Catholic Church and canonized by Pope Pius XI in 1935. During the execution, he said: "I will die as a good servant of the king and the first servant of God". Pope Pius XI canonized More as a martyr in 1935. For his devotion to Catholicism, Mor was canonized by the Roman Catholic Church and canonized by Pope Pius XI in 1935.

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